

Mechanism of Ru(III) Catalysis in Bromamine-T Oxidation of Some Primary Alcohols in Acidic Media

BHARAT SINGH*, N. B. SINGH and B. B. L. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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The sodium salt of *N*-bromo-*p*-toluenesulphonamide, commonly known as bromamine-T (BAT) has been used as an oxidant in Ru(III) catalysed oxidation of methanol and ethanol in acidic media. The oxidation kinetics of these alcohols by bromamine-T in perchloric acid in presence of Ru(III) as catalyst show a first-order dependence on bromamine-T, both substrates, hydrogen ion concentration, ruthenium(III) and inverse first-order on [chloride ion]. No effect of *p*-toluenesulphonamide was evident. Observed stoichiometry, negligible effect of ionic strength and kinetic results point to a mechanism involving interaction between a reactive species of bromamine-T and a transient complex [formed between substrate and ruthenium(III) species] in a rate determining step followed by fast processes regenerating ruthenium(III) species and yielding the final products. Activation parameters have also been calculated.

BROMAMINE-T has been recently used for direct and indirect determination of a variety of substances¹, but no attempt has been made so far to study the oxidation kinetics with this oxidant. It has been observed that the oxidation does not take place either in alkaline or in acidic solutions, but as soon as a catalytic amount of ruthenium(III) chloride solution is introduced in the reaction mixture, the reaction takes place only in acidic media with a measurable velocity. The kinetics of the oxidation of methanol and ethanol by bromamine-T in acidic media in the presence of ruthenium(III) as catalyst has been studied for the first time with a view to throw some light on the oxidation mechanism involving this oxidant. The results are reported in the present communication.

Experimental

Bromamine-T solution was prepared by the method of Nair and Indrasenan¹ and was standardised iodometrically. Chloramine-T (E. Merck, p. a.), *p*-toluenesulphonamide (Koch-Light) and ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Mathey) were used. All other chemicals were of analytical grade. Double distilled water was used throughout the investigations.

The reaction mixture containing substrate, perchloric acid, ruthenium(III) chloride and potassium chloride solutions was allowed to equilibrate for exactly 30 min, after which bromamine-T was added to initiate the reaction. The kinetics were followed by examining aliquots of the reaction mixture for bromamine-T by iodometry.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of alcohols by bromamine-T was investigated at several initial concentrations of the

reactants. First-order dependence in bromamine-T was followed at all initial concentrations of bromamine-T. A linear increase in first order rate constant (k_1) was observed with increase in substrate concentration (Table 1). The reactions therefore have

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS AT 35°

[HClO₄] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M ; [Cl⁻] = 5.00 × 10⁻³ M

10 ³ [Bromamine-T] M	10 ³ [Alcohol] M	10 ⁴ k, sec ⁻¹	
		Methanol ^a	Ethanol ^b
1.00	2.00	1.98	2.06
1.25	2.00	1.98	2.08
1.67	2.00	1.98	2.07
2.00	2.00	1.97	2.06
2.50	2.00	1.99	2.08
3.31	2.00	—	2.07
4.00	2.00	1.99	—
5.00	2.00	1.98	2.11
2.00	1.00	0.99	1.04
2.00	1.30	1.28	1.30
2.00	1.70	1.66	1.73
2.00	2.00	1.99	2.08
2.00	2.50	2.48	2.57
2.00	4.00	3.94	4.40
2.00	5.00	4.98	5.12

^a In presence of 2.64 × 10⁻⁶ M Ru(III) chloride.

^b In presence of 1.76 × 10⁻⁶ M Ru(III) chloride.

first order dependence on [alcohol], and the average second-order constants ($k_2 = k_1/[\text{alcohol}]$) have been calculated as 9.90 ± 0.03 and $10.40 \pm 0.02 \times 10^{-8} \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for the oxidation of methanol and ethanol, respectively under the conditions of Table 1.

A strong dependence of the rate on hydrogen ion concentration was observed under the conditions of Table 2. First-order rate constant increased linearly with increase in [H⁺], indicating first-order dependence on [H⁺]. The average second-order

* Author for correspondence.

sulphonamide.

The oxidising property of bromamine-T in acidic medium is due to the three oxidising species viz., bromamine-T, *p*-toluenesulphobromamide and dibromamine-T.

If BAT is assumed to be the main oxidising species, the reactions would involve an interaction between two similarly charged ions and thus would correspond to a positive ionic strength effect which is contrary to our experimental observations. Thus, the possibility of BAT acting as main oxidising species is ruled out. If DBT is assumed to be the real oxidising species, the reactions would correspond to a negative *p*-toluenesulphonamide effect and second-order dependence on both hydrogen ions and bromamine-T, which are contrary to our experimental results. This rules out the possibility of involvement of DBT in the rate controlling step. So, the only alternative left is the involvement of BAT' as possible oxidising species in the rate determining step. Similar species of chloramine-T has also been reported in acidic medium where H⁺ ions have an acceleration effect on the rate of oxidation of hexacyanoferrate(II)⁸, *p*-cresol⁹ and methyl arylsulphides¹⁰. Thus, from a consideration of this species i.e. BAT' present in the solution and from the results presented above, the following mechanism is suggested where S is methanol or ethanol.

The total Ru(III) concentration may be written as :

$$[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1] + [\text{C}_2] \quad \dots (5)$$

Solving eqn. (5) in terms of [C₂] with the help of steps (i) and (ii) we have

$$[\text{C}_2] = \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{S}][\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{Cl}^-] + K_1(1 + K_2[\text{S}])} \quad \dots (6)$$

Now, the rate of the reaction may be written as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Bromamine-T}]}{dt} = 2k_3[\text{C}_2][\text{BAT}'] \quad \dots (7)$$

Applying the steady state treatment to [BAT'] and making reasonable assumption that [Cl⁻] ≫ K₁(1 + K₂[S]), the following rate law is obtained with the help of eqns. (6) and (7).

$$-\frac{d[\text{Bromamine-T}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_3 K_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bromamine-T}][\text{S}][\text{H}^+][\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{Cl}^-]} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{where } K_3 = \frac{k'_1}{k_{-1}}$$

The above rate law (8) successfully predicts a first-order dependence in bromamine-T, alcohols, hydrogen ion concentration, ruthenium(III) concentration and inverse first-order in chloride ion concentration and also accords well with the stoichiometry, negligible influence of ionic strength and the values of the various activation parameters.

The proposed mechanism involves complex formation between ruthenium(III) species and alcohol prior to the oxidation. The complex formed could not be confirmed, inspite of our best efforts, either spectrophotometrically or by any other means, probably because of the very short life of the activated complex formed which gets disproportionated after its formation via hydride ion transfer (step iv). It seems likely that the mechanism of the reaction is more complicated than the one presented.

A plot of rate against [substrate] or [H⁺] or [Ru(III)]_T or [Cl⁻]⁻¹ at constant [H⁺], [Ru(III)]_T and [Cl⁻] or at constant [substrate], [Ru(III)]_T and [Cl⁻] or at constant [substrate], [H⁺] and [Cl⁻] or at constant [substrate], [H⁺] and [Ru(III)]_T, respectively should give straight lines passing through the origin, and this was found to be so. The values of k₃K₁K₂K₃ in rate law (8) have been calculated from the slopes of the straight lines for substrate, H⁺, Ru(III) and chloride ion variation, respectively and are 2.36 × 10⁸ (substrate variation), 2.32 × 10⁸ (Cl⁻ variation) in oxidation of methanol, while these constants are 3.00 × 10⁸ (substrate variation) 3.07 × 10⁸ (hydrogen ion variation), 3.12 × 10⁸ [Ru(III) variation] and 3.03 × 10⁸ (chloride ion variation) in oxidation of ethanol. The close similarity in k₃K₁K₂K₃ values obtained from various slopes in oxidation of both the alcohols clearly indicates the validity of the rate law (8) and hence, confirms the proposed reaction mechanism.

References

1. G. G. R. NAIR and P. INDRAJENAN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 239.
2. H. H. OGDY and R. E. CONNICK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2646.
3. R. E. CONNICK and D. A. FINE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3414.
4. W. P. GRIFFITH, "The Chemistry of the Rare Platinum Metals", Interscience Publishers, 1967, p. 141.

5. J. HELPERN, B. R. JAMES and A. L. W. KEMP, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4097.
6. J. F. HARROD, S. CICCONE and J. HELPERN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 1372.
7. J. COULL, H. B. HOPE and B. GOUGUELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1489.
8. M. C. AGRAWAL, and S. P. MUSHRAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 838.
9. T. HIGUCHI and A. HUSSAIN, *J. Chem. Soc. B*, 1967, 549.
10. F. RUFF and A. KUCSMAN, *Acta Chem. Acad. Sci. Hung. Tomus*, 1969, **62**, 437.